

Supplementary information to Clinical & Experimental Allergy article:

Specific IgE antibodies of allergic patients were unexpectedly stable during 3 months storage at arbitrary storage temperature

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Figure S1. Detection Schedule Figure A) and Different Sample Storage Conditions B). During the 90-day storage monitoring, the fluctuation ranges of the four temperatures were recorded at the same time (the specific temperatures were recorded every morning and afternoon respectively). Records showed that all of the -80 °C refrigerators were between -78.5 and -81 °C, -20°C refrigerators were between -18 and -21 °C, refrigerated refrigerators were between 2 and 8°C, and room temperature was between 20 and 25 °C (in an air-conditioned environment) within 90 days.

Figure S2. ALLEOS 2000 system detection principle.

Figure S3. Evaluates the stability of the instrument and operating conditions before the start of storage (0 days). The left ordinate (red and black mark) is the serum sIgE antibody titer of each allergen, and the right ordinate (green bar) is the repeatability (CV value) of each allergen at 0 days. Der p- *Dermatophagoides pteronyssinus*. Der f- *Dermatophagoides farinae*. Fel d- *Felis domesticus*. Can f- *Canis familiaris*. Equ c- *Equus caballus*. Gal d- *Gallus domesticus*. Bos d- *Bos domesticus*. Cha f- *Charybdis feriatus*. Pen a- *Penaeus aztecus*. Phl p- *Phleum pratense*. Alt a- *Alternaria alternata*. Bet v- *Betula verrucosa*. Amb a- *Ambrosia artemisiifolia*. Art v-

Artemisia vulgaris. Che l- *Chrysanthemum leucanthemum*. Tar v- *Taraxacum vulgare*.

Figure S4. The mean difference of all detection values of a single allergen within 90 days under different storage methods. Der p- *Dermatophagoides pteronyssinus*. Der f- *Dermatophagoides farinae*. Fel d- *Felis domesticus*. Can f- *Canis familiaris*. Equ c- *Equus caballus*. Gal d- *Gallus domesticus*. Bos d- *Bos domesticus*. Cha f- *Charybdis feriatus*. Pen a- *Penaeus aztecus*. Phl p- *Phleum pratense*. Alt a- *Alternaria alternata*. Bet v- *Betula verrucosa*. Amb a- *Ambrosia artemisiifolia*. Art v- *Artemisia vulgaris*. Che l- *Chrysanthemum leucanthemum*. Tar v- *Taraxacum vulgare*. A1- Stored at - 80 ° C with repeated freezing and thawing. B~L1- Stored at - 80 ° C without repeated freezing and thawing. A2- Stored at -20 ° C with repeated freezing and thawing. B~L2- Stored at -20 ° C without repeated freezing and thawing. A3- Stored at 2-

8 °C. A3- Stored at room temperature (20-25°C). d- days.